

MODIFIED FOURIER TRANSFORM MISALIGNMENT ANALYSIS METHOD FOR MEASURING FIBRE ALIGNMENT IN STITCHED GLASS FABRICS

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Stitched
Fabrics

Fibre
Alignment

Material
Properties

Compression
Strength

To measure fibre alignment in images of dry stitched glass fabrics

- › Using images taken with a standard DSLR camera
 - › Where individual fibres cannot be isolated
 - › At low magnification, containing several fibre tows and several repeating units of stitching
- › With a high degree of spatial resolution
- › With a high degree of accuracy

IMAGE ACQUISITION

Canon 850D DSLR
4000 x 6000 pixels
(24 megapixels)
~162 pixels per mm
~6.2 μm per pixel

MODIFIED FOURIER-TRANSFORM MISALIGNMENT ANALYSIS (FTMA) METHOD

EXISTING FTMA METHOD^[1]

Original
Image

2D Fourier
Transform

Search radii in
 0.1° increments

Identified
feature

[1] K. K. Kratmann, M. P. Sutcliffe, L. T. Lilleheden, R. Pyrz, and O. T. Thomsen, "A novel image analysis procedure for measuring fibre misalignment in unidirectional fibre composites," *Composites Science and Technology*, vol. 69, no. 2, pp. 228–238, Feb. 2009,

COMPUTER-GENERATED IMAGES

Blurred lines with randomly-generated greyscale values

Integer alignments between 0° and 45°

930 x 630 pixels, from which smaller 'cells' are extracted

11 pixels

31 pixels

75 pixels

CELL SIZE AND WINDOWING

Averaged from 500 randomly-selected cells

Absolute deviation $< 0.1^\circ$ for cells greater than 51 pixels

51-pixel cell

Gaussian window:

$$w(n) = \exp \left[-\frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{2\alpha n}{L-1} \right)^2 \right]$$

Increasing α

ALIGNMENT DEPENDENCY

At 0° or 90° , all radii within $\pm\theta/2$ sample the same pixels

At 45° , any deviation from exactly 45° will sample new pixels

Precision depends on the alignment of features in the original cell

$$\theta = 2 \tan^{-1} \left(\frac{1}{2r - 2} \right)$$

ALIGNMENT DEPENDENCY

$$\theta = 2 \tan^{-1} \left(\frac{1}{2r - 2} \right)$$

MULTI-ROTATE METHOD

Cell Rotation
(anticlockwise)

0°

5°

10°

15°

30°

45°

5.4°

4.9°

5.1°

5.1°

5.2°

5.1°

5.13°

Measured Alignment
(rotation corrected)

ANGLE SWEEP AND INCREMENTATION

Known Alignment: 1°

Known Alignment: 45°

APPLICATION ACROSS ANGLES 0°–45°

APPLICATION TO IMAGES OF STITCHED GLASS FABRICS

APPLICATION TO FABRIC IMAGES

VALIDATION

FTMA	-10.97°	5.08°	-2.51°	0.78°
Manual Avg.	-11.06°	5.56°	-2.43°	1.07°
Abs. Diff.	0.09°	0.48°	0.08°	0.29°

The modified FTMA algorithm, with the Multi-Rotate method applied, is able to:

- › Measure fibre alignment in cells with a small number of pixels
 - › With an average accuracy within ± 0.5 degrees, regardless of feature angle
- › Measure fibre alignment in low-magnification photographs of dry stitched glass fabrics
 - › With a level of accuracy that is comparable to a human
 - › At sufficient spatial resolution to identify and segment out features such as stitching

The FTMA Multi-Rotate algorithm can be applied to images from a variety of stitched glass fabrics

Very large amounts of data can be gathered very quickly

Distributions of alignment and key statistical parameters can be extracted

Comparisons can be made of average and maximum misalignment across fabric types

THANK YOU

